

FURTHER STUDIES OF TRANSVERSE IMPACT DAMAGE IN HYBRID COMPOSITE LAMINATES USING A MODIFIED HOPKINSON PRESSURE BAR TECHNIQUE

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ABSTRACT

An improved version of an earlier transverse impact testing technique for composite laminates is described. Force-displacement curves for an all-carbon and a hybrid carbon/glass reinforced laminate impacted at velocities from 3.75 to 7.54 m/s are presented and the resulting damage assessed using C-scan and dye-penetrant soft X-ray techniques, optical microscopy and by determining the residual tensile ply strengths.

INTRODUCTION

The general aim of the research project to which this paper relates was to determine how far the transverse impact resistance of a composite laminate may be improved when a hybrid reinforcing lay-up is used. In preliminary studies [1,2] a full characterization of the loading history during impact was not possible although the resulting damage for both hybrid and non-hybrid laminates could be assessed. Using an improved transverse impact tester it has now become possible to make an unambiguous determination of the load-displacement curve during the transverse impact test. The resulting damage thus may be related to loading history for the given laminate and the impact response of different laminates directly compared.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Circular plate specimens of 80mm diameter were cut from either an all-carbon or a hybrid carbon/glass laminate. Both laminates were hand lay-up, using Ciba-Geigy XD925 epoxy resin, and had 50% fibre content by weight. The all-carbon laminate contained 13 plain-weave carbon reinforcing plies. The hybrid laminate contained a total of 6 plain-weave carbon plies and 20 plain-weave glass plies, with the lay-up sequence (CGGGCGGGCGG)_s. Both laminates had thicknesses of 3.6mm.

The experimental set-up is similar to that previously described [2] except that the projectile and input-bar are now of equal length (0.736m) and both are constructed from 12.7mm diameter annealed, centreless ground Ti 6% Al 4% V alloy bar. The input bar is initially stationary and unstressed and not in contact with the specimen. It is accelerated by impact with the projectile, fired from a small air-gun, to a predetermined velocity and return to the unstressed state before it impacts the specimen. Signals from the two sets of strain gauges on the input-bar were stored in a Datalab type 912 transient recorder and analysed on an IBM PC, using one dimensional elastic wave theory, to obtain the force and displacement histories. A detailed description of the impact tester has been given elsewhere [3].

Force-time and displacement-time curves for an all-carbon specimen impacted at an air gun firing pressure of 15psi, corresponding to an input-bar velocity of 4.0m/s, are shown in Fig. 1. The duration of loading was about 1.6ms, the maximum displacement at the end of the input-bar in contact with the specimen was 1.7mm (about half the plate thickness), and the maximum load was about 3.3kN. The load drop after the initial peak force is thought to be due to initiation of damage.

RESULTS

Impact tests were performed at air gun firing pressures of 15, 40 and 60 psi on the all-carbon and 15, 30, 40 and 60 psi on the hybrid laminates. By cross-plotting the force-time and displacement-time curves for each test, force-displacement curves can be constructed. The area under such curves, to the point at which the force is again zero, represents the energy absorbed during impact. Force-displacement curves for the all-carbon and the hybrid laminates are given in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. For the sake of clarity the curve for the test at 30psi on the hybrid laminate has been omitted.

Figure 1: FORCE-TIME AND DISPLACEMENT-TIME CURVES FOR IMPACT ON ALL-CARBON SPECIMEN

Figure 2: FORCE-DISPLACEMENT CURVES FOR ALL-CARBON LAMINATES

After impact specimens were examined by C-scan to estimate the extent of delamination. A typical C-scan, for the all-carbon specimen impacted at 60psi, is shown in Fig. 4. The delaminated region is seen to be roughly circular. In general, the area of delamination for both laminates, as determined in the C-scan, increases with impact velocity and remains circular in shape. Fig. 5 shows how the average diameter of this region increases with the kinetic energy of the input bar. A very similar response is shown by the two laminates.

Differences between the two laminates are observed, however, when impacted plates are examined under soft X-rays. This is apparent in Fig. 6 which compares radiographs for an all-carbon and a hybrid specimen after impact at 60psi. For the all-carbon laminate the size and shape of the delaminated region (as measured by either technique) is closely similar. For the hybrid laminate, however, the delaminated region is significantly smaller in size when examined under soft X-rays and there is a change in shape indicative of the directionality of the cracking process at the back surface plies. This difference may be due to the greater difficulty in ensuring full penetration of the enhancing dye into the hybrid specimen.

Figure 3: FORCE-DISPLACEMENT CURVES FOR HYBRID LAMINATES

Figure 4: C-SCAN IMAGE FOR ALL-CARBON SPECIMEN IMPACTED AT 60 PSI

Figure 5: AVERAGE DIAMETER OF DELAMINATED ZONE FROM C-SCAN

a) all-carbon

b) hybrid

Figure 6: X-RADIOGRAPHS FOR ALL-CARBON AND HYBRID SPECIMENS IMPACTED AT 60 PSI

Following the C-scan and X-ray examinations specimens were either depled and the residual tensile ply strengths determined or they were sectioned on a diametral plane and examined under the optical microscope. Normalised residual tensile ply strengths for hybrid specimens impacted at 15 and 40 psi are compared in Fig. 7. In each case a much greater reduction in strength is shown by the carbon plies except for those plies close to the mid-thickness region. In contrast the glass plies show little reduction in strength in the test at 40psi while at 60psi, although their strength is reduced to less than 50% of the undamaged strength this reduction is relatively uniform throughout the specimen thickness. Similar studies for the all-carbon laminate have been reported previously [2].

A typical optical micrograph is shown in Fig. 8. This is for an all-carbon specimen after impact at 40 psi, and shows a through-thickness crack, i.e. fibre fracture in all the plies. Also evident from the micrograph are delamination and 45° shear cracks.

Figure 7: NORMALISED RESIDUAL PLY STRENGTHS FOR HYBRID SPECIMENS

DISCUSSION

Previous attempts [1,2] using the Hopkinson Pressure Bar technique to study transverse impact response of composite plates were made difficult by a high frequency and high amplitude noise superimposed on the resulting force-time curves. Using the present modification, this noise is largely eliminated and representative force-time curves can be obtained. For an all-carbon plate impacted at 15psi (Fig. 1), the response was linear elastic up to the maximum load (3.3kN), which is reached after 0.35ms. Wave reflections within the specimen are the likely cause of the two steps on the elastic part of the curve, i.e. for times < 0.35ms. The load drop immediately following the elastic region is thought to be due to fibre fracture in the back surface ply.

From the initial elastic region of the force-displacement curves, Figs. 2 and 3, the plate stiffness for the all-carbon and hybrid lay-ups are found to be 5.0 and 6.0 kN/mm respectively. As both laminates have the same thickness, this confirms that the all-carbon laminate is stiffer than the hybrid laminate. In neither case is the force at a given displacement dependent on the impact velocity, although the range of strain rates encompassed is very small. The effect of increasing impact velocity is merely to increase the maximum displacement. For the hybrid laminate, however, the maximum force increases with displacement, and

Figure 8: OPTICAL MICROGRAPH OF ALL-CARBON SPECIMEN IMPACTED AT 40 PSI

hence with impact velocity, from about 3 to 4.2 kN whereas for the all-carbon laminate the maximum force is about 3kN in all tests. In contrast, the maximum displacement and the total energy absorbed at 60psi firing pressure are greater for the all-carbon laminate, 5.5mm and 9.7J respectively, than for the hybrid laminate, 4.3mm and 5.8J.

It is evident from Figs. 7 and 8 that fibre fracture is more marked in the carbon than the glass plies. This is likely the cause of the greater reduction in stiffness shown by the all-carbon laminate once damage is initiated and the greater maximum deflection. In the hybrid laminates the glass plies inhibit the development of a through thickness crack and so limit the maximum deflection. However, because of the lower modulus and higher failure strain in glass plies, a high percentage of the impact energy is stored as elastic energy in the glass plies instead of causing damage.

CONCLUSIONS

The transverse impact tester based on the Hopkinson Pressure Bar technique has been successfully modified and reliable force-displacement curves have been determined without the need to assume equilibrium in the specimen. Carbon/glass hybrid laminates are more impact damage resistant but absorb less energy at the higher impact velocities than all-carbon laminates. The major energy absorption mechanism for transverse impact loading is by fibre fracturing.

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